

Policy brief

Statsvetenskapliga institutionen
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Scoping Workshop on Collaborative Salmon Research

The RecoSal project

The RecoSal project aims to support collaborative governance for the recovery of a diverse Atlantic salmon population complex in the large River Teno catchment (in Finnish, Tana in Norwegian, and Deatnu in Sámi) in the northernmost Fennoscandia. Through the establishment of collaborations aiming towards a Living Lab (see Living Lab approach, page 2), the project will connect knowledge production with salmon management, with a special emphasis on the development of population-specific, target-based assessments of genetically diverse salmon populations in a multicultural setting that values Indigenous and Local Knowledge (ILK) and rights. RecoSal will provide transdisciplinary advice for designing and implementing effective and socially robust governance and management practices with the aim of ecological conservation and recovery of depleted biodiversity.

"I am concerned about the Tana salmon and the Sámi people of the Tana Valley who fish for salmon. Salmon fishing is our identity and way of life, our food and livelihood. The Tana River has been closed for 3 years now—at least we can still look at it. It is the greatest injustice I know."

(Sámi representative)

Flyfishing wild Atlantic salmon at the bank of Teno River. Photo: Ari Savikko

Map illustrating the study area. The Teno River catchment basin is located between Finland and Norway. Source: Hiedanpää, et al. (2020)

Theoretical framework: Integrative Framework for Collaborative Governance

The Integrative Framework for Collaborative Governance (IFCG) is applied to study and implement collaborative processes in the RecoSal project. The components of the framework are summarized in bullet points below. For more detailed information, see Emerson & Nabatchi (2015).

- System Context consists of different political, legal, socioeconomic, demographic, and environmental conditions.
- Four Drivers emerge that we explore and clarify: Uncertainty, Interdependence, Consequential initiatives and Initiating leadership.
- The System Context and the Drivers provide the impetus for the establishment and formation of what is referred to as Collaborative Governance Regimes, here the potential establishment of Deatnu River Living Lab.
- We apply the concept of Collaboration Dynamics, which consists of three interacting and process-related elements: Principled engagement, Shared motivation and the Capacity for joint action.
- The final variable Generation of Change can be characterized as the production side of collaborative work.

Living Lab approach – Deatnu River Living Lab as an area for collaboration across policy, research and civil society

The Living Lab is envisioned as an outcome after the project end as an arena for collaboration on the future wellbeing of the Teno River among decision-makers (i.e., municipality actors, Sami Parliaments, Tana watercourse fisheries management board (TF), Finnish fishing organizations), researchers from different scientific fields, and civil society such as fishers and knowledge holders. The central actors, their roles and responsibilities in future collaboration will be discussed during the course of four workshops. Our approach was to do smaller meetings in each of the three communities before gathering for larger meetings and Workshops with language interpretation to Finnish, Norwegian and Sámi.

A smaller meeting to introduce the Living Lab concept for local inhabitants and stakeholders in Norway was held in conjunction with a Salmon Dialogue organized by the Nansen Peace Centre and Joddu Wild Salmon Centre. It was held in Tana bru on the 30th of March 2023. The approach to the Living Lab was presented and discussed by those present at the meeting (see Bjärstig & Brattland 2023).

Illustration of the Living Lab approach from the RecoSal project application. Design: Niina Malinen

Camilla Brattland introduces the approach used in the RecoSal project with particular emphasis on traditional knowledge (TK) and Indigenous and Local Knowledge (ILK). Photo: Martin Svenning

Scoping Workshop

A series of four co-design workshops will be held during the RecoSal project’s implementation, where stakeholders will be informed and engaged, and where the project process will be decided upon in a participatory manner, and visions and outcomes discussed. The aim is the establishment of a permanent and long-term collaboration among actors after the project ends (i.e., a Living Lab).

The first workshop was held in Utsjoki, Finland, in March 2023 (see Bjärstig & Brattland 2024). A second, scoping workshop to discuss focal themes, and how to include Indigenous and Local Knowledges (ILK) into ongoing research and collaboration activities took place in Karasjok in the end of November 2023.

The scoping workshop was held immediately following the Salmon Dialogues organized by Joddu- the National Wild Salmon Centre for Norway. This event brought together 30 fishers and knowledge holders from Norway and Finland along the entire Teno River salmon habitat, from the Norwegian coast to the upper tributaries of the river. Among the participating institutions at the scoping workshop were members from Tana Fiskeforvaltning (Tana watercourse fisheries management board), Deatnu salmon fishing region (Finland), Bivdu – coastal salmon fishers association, Laksebreveierne (salmon rights holders), Finnish local fishing organisations, the Wild Salmon Centre, Finnish Sami Parliament, Sami tourism and entrepreneurs’ association (Finland), rod fishers’ associations, and others. Many of these had already participated in the Salmon Dialogues, whereas most of the participants driving from Finland came solely for the workshop.

Before the scoping workshop the participants were asked to give input on themes they would like to discuss and focus on when registering their participation in an online registration form. The scoping workshop started with some introduction from the research team on the approaches used in the RecoSal project when it comes to collaborative processes and ILK, the aims of the scoping workshop, and how it will be conducted. The main themes rendered from the online registration form were also introduced. Participants had conveyed that they wanted to see research on i.e. smolt survival, predators, climate change and salmon industry impacts on salmon, and how traditional knowledge (TK) or ILK could feed into science to co-produce recommendations for salmon management for the future.

Camilla Brattland presents what themes came up as important research topics for the participants. Photo: Jacqueline Moustakas-Verho

Juha Hiedanpää introducing the group work. Photo: Jacqueline Moustakas-Verho

Before the scoping workshop continued in smaller groups there was a presentation round among all participants, where they were asked why they were there and what or who they represented. The presentation sparked some discussion on how the RecoSal project started without asking Sámi people to be part of the project, whether Sámi people now are involved in the project, and what TK or ILK imply. Some of the participants pointed to the lack of early involvement of Sámi, which would have resolved some of these issues at an early stage in the project.

"This meeting should have been held before the project was started. It is against research ethics to launch the project before discussing it with those it concerns. Certain principles need to be clarified before this project can continue, especially regarding the researchers' view on traditional knowledge."

(Workshop participant)

Another issue was how TK and ILK were to be represented in the research project. Several models that had been up for discussion in the Utsjoki kick-off meeting were discussed, such as establishing a reference group as part of the project, or establishing an external board of traditional knowledge holders or experts to give direction to research in general (see Bjärstig & Brattland 2024). Opinions were divided on the nature of TK, to what extent it should be documented to be compatible with research, and the feasibility of having it included in the ongoing scientific monitoring of salmon stocks.

"Traditional knowledge doesn't need to be documented, but if it has to be combined with biological information, then we're in trouble."

(Workshop participant)

Group work

The scoping workshop continued with group work based on the main themes that came up during the preparatory phase and initial presentation and discussion. The main theme all the time was the inclusion of TK/ILK in management. The participants then chose what theme they would like to discuss based on the following themes that had been identified as key to many of the participants: salmon survival, predator effects on smolts and salmon, coastal salmon fishery, rebuilding of salmon stocks, opening of the fishery (for cultural preservation purposes), ecological conditions (i.e. climate change, ice conditions).

The first part of the groupwork (20 minutes) focused on what the main challenges to be researched regarding Tana salmon should be, followed by a second part (20 minutes) discussing participants' ideal solutions, and how research could or should be organized to contribute to solutions.

Group 1 focused on ecological conditions.

The topic was identified by the group as one of the least controversial topics where participants could discuss despite diverging opinions on salmon management. The main challenges identified were ice formation, that ice tends to be melting earlier than before, and behaves differently. Sand banks have also formed, and spawning areas have been destroyed in some areas. Questions arose as to if these should be restored, to let the river flow as it used to? The solution that was put forward was collaboration and discussion with research projects, to investigate whether spawning targets could follow the dynamics of the river better.

Group 2 focused on the opening of fishing.

The main challenges discussed were the abundance of male grills (tintti), what if there are too many of them? Would it be possible to open the fishing only to harvest the male grills? The group also discussed the pros and cons of catch and release, and were concerned with increasing temperatures, which are bringing about more plants and more pikes and

Fishing wild Atlantic salmon. Photo: Ari Savikko

white fish, instead of fostering salmon growth. Solutions put forward included: limit fishing only for persons under 15 or over 75 years old, to preserve transfer of culture between generations; research which salmon stocks there are in the river, at what time and where; and open traditional drift net fishing in a very restricted way during different times of the season than has been done in the past, for example in July, to ensure that different stocks are caught.

Group 3 focused on predators.

The main challenges related to different predators such as fish, birds, seals etc. but also fish farming and bycatch. Problems arise for the populations especially when salmon go out to sea. The participants also argued that there is no good data on predators. Solutions put forward included more studies of what are the biggest predators and how much they are affecting the salmon population. The need to study all predators of salmon simultaneously, and to make use of the locals to find out which predators should be prioritized for research first.

Group 4 also focused on the opening of fishing.

Challenges discussed were fishing in the tributary Ánarjohka,

fish farming in the Tana migration route and what happens at the sea, river mouth, main stem, border rivers, and upper tributaries. The participants argued that since all of the parts of the river are connected with each other, there is a need to see the big picture. The impacts of temperature changes for smolts, i.e. climate change were also discussed, as well as the fact that decisions are not made locally, but in Helsinki and Oslo. In the end, predation and invasive pink salmon populations were also discussed. Solutions put forward were the need for local management, human capacity for local management and management of other species that have an effect on salmon smolts and juveniles. The basis for calculating spawning target (productivity) was in addition perceived as in need to be updated.

All participants then gathered for a plenary session with presentations by group leaders and a big group discussion. The workshop ended with discussions and planning for how the RecoSal project should conduct collaborative research in the future and how to relate to TK and ILK.

Participant sharing the results from the group work in plenary. Photo: Jacqueline Moustakas-Verho

Next step and recommendations

Based on the scoping workshop it became evident that:

- There could have been a better start to the project if locals and Sámi representatives had been involved better and at an early stage. The composition of the research team in regard to acceptance of Indigenous and Local Knowledge systems as valid in research was also questioned by some of the participants.
- What is meant by traditional knowledge or local knowledge is crucial, as it is understood differently and implies different things. Some participants emphasized that traditional and indigenous knowledge have to be part of a reciprocal process, and not only collected upon the questions of researchers. The Sami Parliament of Finland, referring to their new guidelines for research in the field of Sámi cultural heritage and traditional knowledge, emphasized that Sámi need to be involved in determining its use and community consent needs to be given.
- A council for TK/ILK and how to include TK/ILK in research was requested by participants.
- Interviews and surveys could also be used to include TK/ILK, particularly local knowledge on river habitat, according to some participants.
- Ethical guidelines for TK/ILK in research need to be developed and put into use in a more formal way.

Based on this it became evident that the RecoSal project needed to have an ongoing discussion on ethical principles and guidelines with key actors representing the Sámi community and not least the Sami parliaments in Finland and Norway. It was decided to set down a working group to consult the Finnish and Norwegian Sami Parliaments on the best way to proceed with community consent procedures as required by the Sami Parliament of Finland.

Further reading and references:

Bjärstig, T., & Brattland, C. (2024). Recovering diversity in salmon populations and cultures of fishing in the subarctic River Teno – stakeholder meeting and kick-off. Policy Brief 2024:2 . Department of Political Science, Umeå University. <https://umu.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1901143/FULLTEXT01.pdf>

Bjärstig, T., & Brattland, C. (2023). Presentation “Introduksjon til prosjektet RecoSal og LivingLab” and meeting notes from meeting in Tana bru. RecoSal project.

Emerson, K., & Nabatchi, T. (2015). Collaborative Governance Regimes. Georgetown University Press.

Hiedanpää, J., Sajets, J., Jounela, P., Jokinen, M., & Sarkki, S. (2020). Beliefs in conflict: The management of Teno Atlantic salmon in the Sámi Homeland in Finland. Environmental Management, 66, 1039-1058.

Project partners

Jaakko Erkinaro (project coordinator), Juha Hiedanpää, Mikko Jokinen, Henni Pulkinen, Niina Malinen, Jacqueline Moustakas-Verho, Taru Rikkonen and Antti Rätty from the Natural Resources Institute Finland (Luke); Camilla Brattland and Torstein Pedersen from UiT - the Arctic University of Norway; Martin Svenning and Morten Falkegård from the Norwegian Institute for Nature Research (NINA); and Therese Bjärstig from Umeå University, Sweden.

Authors: Therese Bjärstig, Camilla Brattland and Taru Rikkonen

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Malin Eklund Wimelius

Contact

Department of Political Science, Umeå University

Department of Political Science

Umeå University

www.umu.se/department-of-political-science/

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